

Linking Logic and Comprehension: The Relationship Between Logical-Mathematical Intelligence and Critical Reading Skills Among STEM Students

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between logical-mathematical intelligence and critical reading skills among STEM students at San Mariano National High School–Main during the school year 2025–2026. Specifically, it aimed to determine the levels of students’ logical-mathematical intelligence and critical reading skills, and to assess whether a significant relationship exists between these variables. A quantitative correlational research design was employed, involving 117 respondents selected through proportional stratified random sampling from a population of 165 STEM students. Data were collected using adapted and modified assessment tools measuring logical reasoning and critical reading abilities. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, including mean and standard deviation, and inferential statistics using Pearson’s r at a 0.05 level of significance. The results indicated that most students demonstrated moderate levels of logical-mathematical intelligence, while their critical reading skills varied across sections. A weak but statistically significant positive correlation ($r = 0.201$, $p = 0.031$) was found, suggesting that students with higher logical reasoning ability tend to exhibit better critical reading performance. The findings suggest that enhancing logical-mathematical intelligence may contribute to improving students’ comprehension and analytical abilities. The study recommends the integration of logic-based and problem-solving strategies into reading instruction to foster more balanced cognitive and academic development among STEM learners.

Keywords: critical reading, logical-mathematical intelligence, STEM education

Introduction

Students taking the STEM strand need to develop strong reading comprehension and logical reasoning skills. These skills are essential for understanding scientific texts, solving problems, and analyzing data. However, most senior high school students struggle with reading comprehension, especially when dealing with complex written texts, even though they tend to perform well in mathematical calculations. This shows that while many students find reading comprehension challenging, their logical-mathematical skills and math proficiency are often more developed in the STEM strand (Arofah et al., 2024; Noor et al., 2022; Ragudo, 2024). This situation highlights the need to understand the connection between logical-mathematical

intelligence and critical reading skills to promote better learning and balanced cognitive development among STEM students.

Understanding this interaction begins with the concept of logical-mathematical intelligence. Gardner (1983) originally defined this as the ability to think logically, compute mathematically, and approach problems scientifically. Students possessing this trait organize ideas and recognize patterns effectively to solve problems they are faced with. Rather than just applying to numbers, this intelligence allows students to relate concepts across different scientific contexts, which Prastika et al. (2021) and Nursoffina and Efendi (2022) identified as a key factor in STEM success. When students use this logical and reflective thinking, they develop metacognitive awareness that lets them evaluate their own learning (Kathayat, 2024; Nordin et al., 2024). Nurhidayati et al. (2024) pointed out that this type of intelligence reinforces higher-order thinking skills necessary for comprehensive data analysis. The mental processes involved here—analysis, organization, and evaluation—are the exact same mechanisms required to process and understand complex written texts.

Reading critically involves much more than just processing words on paper; it demands readers to analyze arguments, examine evidence, and make conclusions based on what they read about. Fazliddinovich (2025) writes that reading improves higher-order thinking because readers actively challenge the validity of ideas. This active engagement becomes richer when readers connect new information to what they already know (Abahussain et al., 2022). Such a connection reflects the Schema Theory of Bartlett (1932) and Anderson (1977), which suggests that learning is most effective when it links up to existing knowledge structures in the brain. Organizing this information logically is what enables readers to make stronger connections among ideas (Anderson, 2017; Shinta et al., 2025). Building these logical structures in reading requires specific teaching methods in the classroom.

Teachers apply various techniques to combine logical reasoning and reading development. For instance, Problem-Based Learning makes students more involved and helps them grasp STEM lessons better through active problem-solving (Maidan et al., 2020). Designing lessons around the Multiple Intelligences Theory also improves student confidence and mathematical literacy (Hidayat & Mahmudi, 2025). Practical problem-solving exercises, as Mukhlisin et al. (2023) stated, promote deep learning and reasoning. Methods that encourage collaboration and critical thinking help students understand data more effectively (Marković & Vukadin, 2019). These interactive and student-centered approaches show that simultaneously developing reasoning and reading makes learning meaningful. The Philippine educational system attempts to integrate these very approaches into its national curriculum.

The Department of Education emphasizes the combined development of logical reasoning and literacy for STEM education in the Philippines. Republic Act No. 10533, or the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, requires schools to improve critical thinking and problem-solving across all subjects. To support this, DepEd Order No. 35, s. 2016 established the Learning Action Cell to help teachers improve their methods for student analytical and reading abilities (Department of Education, 2013, 2016). The K to 12 Curriculum further encourages higher-order thinking through inquiry-based classes (Department of Education, n.d.). Researchers have observed how these policies play out in actual classrooms. Lansangan and Orleans (2024) discovered that reasoning-based activities improve the analytical comprehension of students, while Villanueva et al. (2023) reported that the MATATAG curriculum promotes reflective learning. Eslit (2023), MI School (2025), and Banate and Bauyot (2025) argued that literacy and logic must go hand in hand to achieve academic success. This local emphasis aligns with broader findings on how reasoning and comprehension affect overall student performance.

Many studies confirm that logical reasoning and reading comprehension reinforce each other. Students who reason logically excel at understanding and resolving complex issues (Can, 2020; Del Rosario, 2020), and those with good reading comprehension have better outcomes in math word problems (Hadianto et al., 2021; Wikanengsih & Rizqiya, 2020). Applying questioning techniques improves comprehension because students critically think about the text (Henny et al., 2022). Arofah et al. (2024) and Susandi et al. (2024) established that academic performance improves when schools nurture logical and reading abilities simultaneously, while Valenzuela et al. (2023) noted that poor comprehension makes analytical problems difficult to solve. Local research mirrors these findings, showing that STEM students with good logical intelligence perform better (Cabuquin, 2022), and comprehension skills relate highly to math performance (Cabansag, 2024; Recanil & Quirante, 2025). Students who struggle with reading find it difficult to solve problems overall (Luna et al., 2023; Tan, 2023). Developing critical thinking improves overall learning (Pacis, 2024; Pilande, 2023), even though anxiety sometimes impairs reasoning (Dela Cruz, 2022). Teachers use creative materials (Balite & Cajandig, 2024) and paraphrasing tasks (Delideli, 2024) to increase motivation and logic.

Although many researchers have explored logical-mathematical intelligence and reading comprehension, few have examined their direct relationship among STEM students in the Philippines. Most existing studies focused on only one skill or on general academic performance, leaving limited evidence on how these two variables influence each other in actual learning settings. This gap shows the need to investigate the connection between logical-mathematical intelligence and critical reading skills in STEM students.

This study aims to address the understanding of how logical-mathematical intelligence and critical reading skills are associated among STEM students at San Mariano National High School – Main. Specifically, this study aims to: (1) determine the level of logical-mathematical intelligence among STEM students; (2) determine the level of critical reading skills among STEM students; and (3) examine whether a significant relationship exists between logical-mathematical intelligence and critical reading skills among STEM students.

Methods

Research Design

For this study, the researchers used the correlational type of design to provide a detailed explanation of the target variables. The purpose of the study is to identify the relationship between logical-mathematical intelligence and critical reading skills among STEM students. Correlational research is a type of non-experimental research that easily predicts and explains the relationship among the variables (Seeram, 2019). The correlational design yields either positive or negative results, and the variables cannot be controlled or manipulated by the researchers (Bhandari, 2023).

Participants and Locale

The participants of this study are the STEM academic students enrolled in San Mariano National High School for the school year 2025–2026. The total population consists of 165 students distributed across four sections: Grade 11 STEM Pythagoras (37), Grade 11 STEM Archimedes (39), Grade 12 STEM Euler (45), and Grade 12 STEM Lavoisier (44).

The researchers used probability sampling, as this method is appropriate for a correlational research design that requires representativeness of the sample. Using Slovin's Formula with a 5% margin of error and 95% confidence level, the computed sample size from a

population of 165 is 117 respondents. The type of probability sampling that the researchers utilized is proportional stratified random sampling. Table 1 shows the proportional distribution of respondents per section.

Table 1
Population and Sample Size

Grade and Section	Population (n)	Proportion (%)	Sample (n)
Grade 11 – Pythagoras	37	22%	26
Grade 11 - Archimedes	39	24%	28
Grade 12 – Euler	45	27%	32
Grade 12 - Lavoisier	44	27%	31
Total	165	100%	117

Instrumentation

In this research study, the researchers adapted and modified existing standardized tests to collect data on the two variables: Logical-Mathematical Intelligence (LMI) and Critical Reading Skills (CRS).

To measure Logical-Mathematical Intelligence, the researchers used the Logical Reasoning Practice Test developed by the Dronacharya Group of Institutions (2019). The tool comprises multiple-choice questions based on number series, patterns, and logic puzzles to check problem-solving and reasoning skills. The test comprises 15 questions, scored dichotomously where one point is given for every correct answer and zero for an incorrect response. Higher scores imply higher logical-mathematical intelligence. The scores are interpreted using the following standard scale: 1.00–8.00 (Low), 8.01–11.50 (Moderate), and 11.51–15.00 (High).

To assess Critical Reading Skills, the researchers adapted the Test of Scientific Literacy Skills (TOSLS) originally developed by Gormally et al. (2012). The instrument was modified to involve short texts and 15 multiple-choice items necessitating higher-order thinking skills, including argument analysis, evidence evaluation, and inference making. The test is scored similarly, awarding one point per correct response. To maintain consistency in interpreting the data across both variables, the researchers applied the same 15-point interpretation scale: 1.00–8.00 (Low), 8.01–11.50 (Moderate), and 11.51–15.00 (High).

Data Collection

Prior to the study, formal letters of request were prepared by the researchers and sent to the principal of San Mariano National High School-Main requesting prior approval to conduct the research. Permission was obtained from the principal and research adviser in their official capacity.

During the actual data gathering, the researchers arranged with subject teachers to administer the tests without interfering with regular classes. The research objectives were explained beforehand, and informed consent forms were obtained from respondents prior to distributing the instruments. Respondents were assured of their voluntary participation and the confidentiality of their information. To avoid the disruption of classes, the researchers explicitly instructed the respondents that the answer sheets would be collected during their recess time on the day of the conduct.

After the conduct of the tests, the collected data were encoded into a spreadsheet compatible with Jamovi software. The data gathered were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics involving mean, and standard deviation were used to determine the levels of logical–mathematical intelligence and critical reading skills of the respondents. Pearson’s *r* correlation was used to test the significance of the relationship between logical–mathematical intelligence and critical reading skills at a 0.05 level of significance.

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to ethical standards in conducting research involving human participants. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents before their participation. Participation in the study was entirely voluntary, and students were given the right to decline or withdraw at any point without consequence. To ensure data privacy and confidentiality, no personally identifiable information was collected or disclosed. Anonymity was strictly maintained through the use of codes instead of names. The instruments used were appropriate for the respondents’ level and did not include any sensitive or harmful content.

Results and Discussion

Prior to inferential analysis, parametric assumptions were tested with Shapiro-Wilk for normality and Levene’s test for Heteroscedasticity. None of the *p*-values were significant indicating that no violation was found in the data set.

Level of Logical-Mathematical Intelligence

Table 2 shows the logical reasoning scores of the four sections. The results reveal that the Euler, Lavoisier, and Pythagoras sections have a moderate level of logical reasoning (*M* = 9.65, 9.10, and 9.12). This means that most of the students in these sections can solve basic mathematical problems and analyze standard situations. On the other hand, Archimedes is at a low level (*M* = 7.93), which means that the students in this section find it difficult to solve mathematical problems and analyze complex numerical situations.

Table 2
Level of Logical-Mathematical Intelligence of STEM Students

Section	<i>n</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	Verbal Interpretation
Archimedes	28	7.93	1.63	Low
Euler	31	9.65	2.89	Moderate
Lavoisier	31	9.10	2.60	Moderate
Pythagoras	26	9.12	2.39	Moderate

These findings show that although some students show fair reasoning ability, most still need significant improvement in analyzing and drawing logical conclusions. What is happening is that students are entering the STEM strand with widely varying foundational skills. According to Gardner (1983), this intelligence is the ability to think logically and approach problems scientifically. The moderate and low scores suggest that many respondents struggle to organize ideas and recognize patterns effectively. Prastika et al. (2021) and Nursoffina and Efendi (2022) clarified that students with greater logical-mathematical intelligence exhibit better problem-solving capabilities because they relate concepts across different scientific contexts. This explains why some sections perform moderately while another remains low.

When students lack this logical and reflective thinking, they fail to develop the metacognitive awareness needed to evaluate their own learning (Kathayat, 2024; Nordin et al., 2024). Furthermore, Nurhidayati et al. (2024) pointed out that this type of intelligence reinforces higher-order thinking skills necessary for comprehensive data analysis. The data imply that simply being enrolled in STEM does not automatically equip students with these advanced logical abilities they are faced with. Mukhlisin et al. (2023) added that practical problem-solving approaches build critical thinking and intellectual abilities, which are key aspects needed to improve their logical reasoning capacity.

Level of Critical Reading Skills

Table 3 presents the critical reading skills of the same sections. The data shows that Euler, Archimedes, and Pythagoras achieved a high level of critical reading ($M = 12.0, 12.0, \text{ and } 12.7$). This indicates that the students in these sections have good critical reading skills and can understand and analyze texts well. Lavoisier performed at a moderate level ($M = 11.3$), suggesting an average performance in critical reading. The basis of interpretation was standardized across all sections to reflect the true mathematical weight of the means.

Table 3
Level of Critical Reading Skills of STEM Students

Section	<i>n</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	Verbal Interpretation
Archimedes	28	12.0	2.13	High
Euler	31	12.0	3.54	High
Lavoisier	31	11.3	3.11	Moderate
Pythagoras	26	12.7	1.81	High

From this, students generally have a stronger ability to understand and evaluate information critically when presented in text rather than through logical puzzles. Fazliddinovich (2025) stated that critical reading improves higher-order thinking by encouraging active questioning, analysis, and synthesis of information. This reflects why most students perform highly; they actively challenge the validity of ideas they read about. Their high performance can also be explained by the Schema Theory of Bartlett (1932) and Anderson (1977), which suggests that learning is most effective when it links up to existing knowledge structures in the brain. Abahussain et al. (2022) reiterated that this active engagement becomes richer when readers connect new information to what they already know.

Because the students can organize this information logically, they make stronger connections among ideas (Anderson, 2017; Shinta et al., 2025). Lansangan and Orleans (2024) discovered that reasoning-based classroom activities improve the analytical comprehension of students. This shows that the current instructional methods, which promotes reflective learning (Villanueva et al., 2023), are effectively developing students’ text-based critical reading levels. Banate and Bauyot (2025) emphasized that effective STEM education enhances reading for meaning, supporting the idea that schools are successfully integrating these approaches into their classes.

Relationship Between Logical-Mathematical Intelligence and Critical Reading Skills

Table 4 shows the statistical test of the relationship between the two primary variables. The correlational table indicates a weak positive relationship ($r = 0.201$) between critical reading skills and logical reasoning, with a *p*-value of 0.031.

Table 4

Relationship Between Logical-Mathematical Intelligence and Critical Reading Skills

Variables	M	SD	r	p-value	Decision
Critical reading skills	12.0	2.68	0.201	0.031	Reject Ho
Logical reasoning	8.97	2.49			

Since the p-value (0.031) is less than the 0.05 level of significance, the relationship is deemed statistically significant. This means there is a small but significant connection between the variables: students with better critical reading skills also tend to have better logical reasoning. However, the weak correlation ($r = 0.201$) implies that logical reasoning only relates to a very small portion of reading comprehension ability.

But even with a weak connection, the mental processes involved in logic, like pattern recognition, partially support the synthesis of evidence in reading. Can (2020) and Del Rosario (2020) described that students who reason logically excel at understanding and resolving complex issues. Similarly, Hadiananto et al. (2021) and Wikanengsih and Rizqiya (2020) found that those with good reading comprehension have better outcomes in math word problems. This shows that comprehension skills relate highly to math performance, and ability in reading is as necessary as computation (Cabansag, 2024; Recanil & Quirante, 2025).

On the other hand, Valenzuela et al. (2023) noted that poor comprehension makes analytical problems difficult to solve. Luna et al. (2023) and Tan (2023) elaborated that students who struggle with reading find it difficult to solve problems overall. Cabuquin (2022) found that logical-mathematical intelligence remains essential for academic success, showing its connection with comprehension and reasoning abilities that students rely on. Ultimately, Arofah et al. (2024) and Susandi et al. (2024) established that academic performance improves when schools nurture logical and reading abilities simultaneously, proving that literacy and logic must go hand in hand (Eslit, 2023; MI School, 2025).

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concludes that enrollment in the STEM strand does not automatically equip students with high logical-mathematical intelligence, even if they possess strong critical reading skills. The weak connection between these variables indicates a cognitive imbalance where students rely heavily on language schemas and textual structures to process information rather than pure mathematical logic they are faced with. This practically shows that the cognitive bridge between analyzing numerical patterns and synthesizing textual evidence remains underdeveloped. Teachers cannot assume that STEM students naturally possess the logical reasoning required for complex scientific problems. Educational strategies must deliberately integrate logical problem-solving into reading exercises to build these parallel mental processes simultaneously.

While this research establishes a vital baseline, it is limited by its correlational design and localized sample at San Mariano National High School, which restricts the ability to determine causal effects. Future researchers should perform experimental studies to test specific instructional methods that might strengthen the cognitive link between reading and logic across larger populations. School administrators and curriculum developers are advised to design interventions that force students to apply critical reading in mathematical contexts, such as complex word problems. Furthermore, subject teachers must collaborate to ensure that literacy

and mathematical logic do not operate in isolation but work together to improve the overall academic performance of students.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) Declaration Statement

The authors used ChatGPT as a generative AI tool to assist in grammar refinement and clarity of construction of the paper during manuscript preparation. Additionally, Perplexity AI was utilized to support the organization and preliminary verification of references. All AI-assisted content was carefully reviewed, edited, and verified by the authors to ensure accuracy, originality, and proper citation.